

The Challenge

In the face of a changing climate, **cities are becoming increasingly exposed to extreme weather events**. Extreme temperature events such as **heatwaves** are becoming longer, more frequent and intense in cities, affecting society's most vulnerable populations, as well as health and energy sectors. Identifying vulnerable neighbourhoods within cities, projecting future climate scenarios, and understanding sector impacts from extreme temperature events are vital for addressing vulnerabilities, fostering resilience, and creating effective local adaptation strategies.

Action

CLIM4cities will pioneer the development of **Machine Learning** and **Artificial Intelligence** models to downscale air and land surface temperature predictions in urban areas by a factor of ten. This involves collecting and quality-controlling citizen observations and numerical weather prediction data, then combining this with processed **Earth Observation** data and physics-based predictors. The resulting Machine Learning Database will be used to train and test the models, enabling **low-cost, integrated urban climate services**.

The Solution

CLIM4cities will demonstrate a **scalable solution** for European cities by using Danish case studies to showcase a Proof of Concept Application featuring **downscaled short-term predictions and climate change scenarios**. This Proof of Concept framework builds on previous pilot implementations in Lisbon and Naples, providing a strong foundation for future development as a **tool for local authorities** to:

- Identify short-term critical areas of the city during heat- and coldwave events
- Test the performance of urban development scenarios in response to climate change and urban spatial planning policies
- Translate essential climate variables into impact indicators relevant to the health and energy sectors

Impact

CLIM4cities will contribute to scientific advances and user uptake of Earth Observation data. **CLIM4cities** brings added value information to society by contributing to the international efforts on addressing key urban climate monitoring and local climate change adaptation challenges by bringing the Earth Observation and crowdsourced-based Machine Learning models closer to user requirements for local operational climate and weather monitoring services.

Who is CLIM4cities for?

- City planners
- Policymakers
- Researchers and Academics
- Local authorities and Early Warning Systems
- Health and Energy Sectors
- Technology and Innovation Enthusiasts

Project Snapshot

CLIM4cities is a 1-year European Space Agency funded project under the call for AI Trustworthy Applications for Climate.

Project Members

Danish
Meteorological
Institute

CoLAB
+ATLANTIC

CLIM4cities is coordinated by the Danish Meteorological Institute.